

Jigging for Squid: a little biology on a physical oceanography cruise.

Photo credit: Lindsay Wentzel, East Carolina University, Coastal Studies Institute

RR2407 Cruise Report

June 6–11, 2024

Morehead City, NC to Woods Hole, MA

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1 Introduction and Overview of the Projects

Cruise RR2407 departed from Morehead City, NC, on June 6, 2024, and arrived in Woods Hole, MA, on June 11, 2024. The Science Party aboard RR2407 was involved in several complementary projects, funded by various sources, in addition to an extensive outreach and training effort on this transit cruise, which was also the final segment of R/V *Roger Revelle*'s move from the Pacific to the North Atlantic for a series of cruises in 2024.

Figure 1: Regional context for the MAB-SWOT array, which was deployed on the shoreward flank of the Gulf Stream just downstream of its separation from the continental slope where the Gulf Stream crosses isobaths and is transitioning from an "attached" western boundary current to a meandering "free jet." Blue swaths show the U.S. East Coast SWOT crossover region. This region is where SWOT provided once-per-day coverage (in the lighter shaded areas) or twice-per-day coverage (in the darker shaded diamonds) during the 90-day Cal/Val period. The MAB-SWOT array was within the westernmost diamond. Light contours indicate sea surface height (SSH) isolines from the mean altimetry, and gray shading represents SSH variance. Cape Hatteras (star), MAB shelf (MAB), and South Atlantic Bight shelf (SAB) are indicated as is the shelf break, nominally at the 200-m isobath (heavy contour). *Figure courtesy of R. Todd.*

1.1 CPIES Recoveries: the MAB-SWOT/NGIW-IWR Array

RR2407 served as the recovery cruise for some of the *in situ* instruments that were part of an array deployed through the Mid-Atlantic Bight-Surface Water Ocean Topography [MAB-SWOT](#) project which "adopted" the SWOT crossover site east of Cape Hatteras (Figure 1). During the 90-day SWOT Cal/Val period (nominally April 4, 2023, through July 4, 2023), there was rapid sampling (twice per day) by the new National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) [SWOT satellite](#) in this region. The MAB-SWOT project is endorsed by and falls under the [SWOT Adopt a Crossover Consortium](#). Measurements from the *in situ* instruments comprising

current and pressure sensor equipped inverted echo sounders (CPIESs), gliders, and a moored Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP)—together with measurements from several shore-based high-frequency (HF) radar installations—were collected along and offshore of the MAB for 18 months (January 2023–June 2024) that included the Cal/Val period of the SWOT satellite mission.

The MAB-SWOT project dovetails with a broader National Ocean Partnership Program (NOPP) Global Internal Waves (NGIW) effort to obtain *in situ* measurements of internal waves globally through the deployment of relocatable [Internal Wave Resolving \(IWR\) arrays](#) for assessment and improvement of high-resolution ocean general circulation models that include tidal forcing and provide boundary conditions for regional models. The high-frequency *in situ* measurements from the IWR arrays are intended to resolve the energy flux associated with internal waves that propagate through the deep ocean. The full IWR arrays combine a central full-water column mooring with a high vertical resolution to resolve the waves' modal structure surrounded by an antenna of vertically integrated measures of variability from the CPIESs to resolve the speed and direction of beam propagation. In the case of the MAB-SWOT array, however, only a partial IWR array was deployed, and the central mooring was replaced by a station-keeping Spray glider. This decision was made in part because of the expectation of severe mooring blow-down by the Gulf Stream current, which would have damaged the central mooring.

The goals of the combined MAB-SWOT/NGIW-IWR array are to:

- (1) advance the community's dynamical understanding of the key oceanographic region east of Cape Hatteras, where the Gulf Stream leaves the continental margin and crosses over the Deep Western Boundary Current and where there are vigorous shelf/ocean exchanges and complex sub-mesoscale dynamics associated with entrainment of shelf waters in the Gulf Stream North Wall;
- (2) validate measurements provided by the SWOT satellite mission; and (3) provide measures of the internal tides for a comprehensive comparison with output from global ocean general circulation models that include [tidal forcing](#).

1.2 CPIES Deployments: Pioneer-adjacent PDS-PIES

RR2407 also served as the deployment cruise for two instruments on the continental slope adjacent to the southern MAB shelf (Figure 5). These instruments are deployed just offshore of the Ocean Observatories Initiative (OOI) Pioneer Array, which was relocated to the region in April 2024 (Figure 2). The instruments are Popeye Data Shuttle-enabled current and pressure sensor equipped inverted echo sounders (PDS-PIESs). They will be deployed for four years (recovery planned for 2028) with PDS pods that ascend annually to the sea surface to return data batches via a satellite link.

Figure 2: Map of Popeye Data Shuttle-enabled current and pressure sensor equipped inverted echo sounders (PDS-PIESs) (red dots, C1: 36°3.125' N; 74°42.365' W and C2: 35°42.005' N; 74°46.209' W), Pioneer moorings (yellow dots), and nominal offshore Pioneer glider line (blue). The red curve is the time-averaged position of the Gulf Stream core, and the dotted lines are Jason altimeter tracks. Heavy contours are the 200-m and 1000-m isobaths.

The goals for the PDS-PIES deployments are to:

- (1) capture mesoscale variability offshore of the Pioneer Array;
- (2) capture western excursions of the Gulf Stream North Wall that may influence ocean-shelf exchange; and
- (3) observe the upper portion of the equatorward-flowing Deep Western Boundary Current, where it squeezes under the poleward flowing Gulf Stream.

The PDS-PIESs are deployed 40 km apart on the 1000-m isobath to extend the Pioneer Array mooring footprint offshore and to allow comparison with an OOI glider that is running a line (nominally) along the 1000-m isobath.

Figure 3: Map of the cruise region with planned locations of the CRIES operations in the blue box, the Gulf Stream shingle operations in the purple box, and the New England Shelf operations in the magenta box. Color shading is SSH from absolute dynamic topography from Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS). The thick black line is the Gulf Stream path identified by the 25-cm SSH contour. The thin black dashed lines show isobaths at 100 m, 1000 m, and 4000 m depths. The yellow star is the location of Morehead City, NC. The magenta star is the location of Woods Hole, MA. The blue diamonds denote the planned drifter deployment locations. The inverted purple triangles denote the planned XBT deployment locations. The yellow circle denotes the planned locations of CTD casts. Planned deployment locations and actual deployment locations were approximately the same. See the eLog at the end of the document for exact locations.

1.3 Adaptive Sampling, Outreach, and Synergies

During the 450 nautical mile transit from the study site northeast of Cape Hatteras to Woods Hole (Figure 3, Figure 4), adaptive sampling, guided by satellite observations, was conducted to examine mesoscale and submesoscale features along the Gulf Stream North Wall, in the Slope Sea and on the MAB shelf. The sampling included a collection of underway shipboard data, which included measurements from the thermosalinograph, the shipboard ADCP, and the Hydrographic Doppler Sonar System (HDSS), as well as

conductivity-temperature-depth (CTD) casts to measure a suite of upper-ocean properties and launches of expendable bathythermograph (XBT) probes to measure upper-ocean temperature profiles.

The cruise provided at-sea experiences for four Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) - Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI) Joint Program (JP) students and four undergraduates from the University of Massachusetts Dartmouth as part of their spring 2024 [Blue Economy Program](#) experience with WHOI. On the cruise, two of the JP students (Perez and Enders) served as watch leaders and mentors to the Blue Economy undergrads. Also, they served as leads for the adaptive sampling program.

During the cruise, twelve drifters (Table 4) were deployed for the Lagrangian Drifter Laboratory at Scripps Institution of Oceanography (SIO) to obtain measurements for the 2024 North Atlantic hurricane season. RR2407 also served as a University of Hawaii Data Acquisition System (UHDAS) training cruise for University of Hawaii Currents Group members and the Joint Archive for Shipboard ADCP (JASADCP).

1.4 Funding Sources

The MAB-SWOT project ("*SWOT Adopt-A-Crossover Field Campaign-Cape Hatteras*") is funded by NASA through the Ocean Physics Program (grant no. 1687411) with a contract to the University of North Carolina Chapel Hill (UNC) and with subcontracts to WHOI and Coastal Studies Institute/East Carolina University (CSI). The lead PI is Harvey Seim (UNC) and co-PIs are Robert Todd and Magdalena Andres (WHOI), and Mike Muglia (CSI). The IWR arrays are funded through a NOPP NGIW project ("*A Distributed Network of Internal Wave Resolving Moored Arrays for Assessing Tide-Resolving Model Fields and Improve Forecasts in the Coastal Ocean*") awarded to SIO (grant no. N000142212575) with subawards to WHOI and NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL). The lead PI is Amy Waterhouse (SIO), and co-PIs are Drew Lucas and Uwe Send (SIO), Magdalena Andres and Tom Farrar (WHOI), and Jinbo Wang (JPL).

The MAB-SWOT deployment cruise in January 2023 aboard R/V *Neil Armstrong* (AR71) was part of a Woods Hole, MA to Pensacola, FL transit with NASA providing funding for a ship day to deploy the 6 CPIESs and conduct full-water column CTD casts at each CPIES site. The recovery cruise in June 2024 aboard R/V *Roger*

Figure 4: A still from a video of the cruise operations put together by Jamie Ash of the UH Currents Group. A link to the video can be found in Section 9.2. Color shading is the sea surface temperature of June 8, 2024, from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration’s (NOAA) geo-polar blended product, which has a resolution of 0.05° (≈ 5 km). The gray Xs are locations of deployed Pioneer PIES. The black Xs are the locations of the remaining SWOT PIES that could not be recovered. The black pluses are locations of CTD casts. The grey and black dots are the locations of the deployed surface velocity program (SVP) drifters and directional wave spectra barometer (DWSB) drifters, respectively. The large black circle shows the ship’s location throughout the video. *Video and figure courtesy of J. Ash.*

Revelle (RR2407) was embedded in the transit to Woods Hole, MA (that marked the beginning of 6 months of work for *Revelle* in the North Atlantic as part of the Office of Naval Research (ONR) Task Force Ocean New England Seamounts Acoustics Experiment) with two ship days for the science objectives supported by ONR through NOPP NGIW program. The purchase of the CPIES instruments was supported through an ONR Defense University Research Instrumentation Program (DURIP) award (grant no. N000142212209) to WHOI with the instrument batteries and other expendables supported by the WHOI sub-award from NASA/UNC. NASA/UNC support also funded all RR2407 cruise-related expenses (salary, travel, shipping) and salary for

data processing (Level 0-2) and data dissemination Wang and Andres, 2024a, 2024b. The WHOI Academic Programs Office provided support for two of the Blue Economy students' participation on RR2407.

The National Science Foundation (NSF) Division of Ocean Sciences Physical Oceanography program funded the PDS-PIES deployments through a grant (OCE-2414853) to M. Andres at WHOI ("*RAPID: A Cost-Effective Approach for Characterizing Variability at High Temporal Resolution for Long Duration on the Continental Slope of the Southern Mid-Atlantic Bight.*")

2 Cruise Narrative

We arrived at the Morehead City, NC port on Thursday, June 6, 2024. Security in the port was very tight: Transportation Worker Identification Credential (TWIC) cardholders were allowed on/off the ship but could not serve as escorts for their cruise mates. We needed a Port Police escort for all non-TWIC cardholders.

The load was light: two PIES drums and three wire baskets from WHOI, and two pallets of drifters from SIO. O. E. Durant served as chandler (contact Nolan Ferrer), and the Agent was Trevor Bowman of Norton Lilly. The ship left Morehead City at 16:00 local time, and the steam to the first site (C2) was approximately 12 hours.

We arrived near the C2 site on Friday, June 7, 2024, and started recovering a Spray glider (SN 62) at 0500. The glider had been deployed in Miami, FL, on April 10, 2024, by Robert Todd's WHOI glider group and suffered a broken tail fin on May 30, 2024, as it was approaching the Cape Hatteras region. The glider was recovered at 35°42.210' N; 74°43.763' W and was aboard by 0609. Once the glider data are post-processed, plots of the glider mission (ID 24406201) will be available [here](#).

After that, we moved to site C2, where we deployed a CPIES (SN 462) with a current meter (SN 270) and four PDSs (SN 168-171) as part of an NSF-funded RAPID project. The instrument was set to sample round trip vertical acoustic travel time (τ) with bursts of 16 12-kHz pings (alternating at 16 s and 18 s intervals) every 10 minutes and pressure and current measurements every 30 minutes. PDS pods are scheduled to launch on

Figure 5: Map of the PIES site with locations of the SWOT PIES (**P1–P6**) are denoted by magenta circles and the Pioneer PIES (**C1–C2**) by purple squares. Color shading is SSH from absolute dynamic topography. The thick black line is the Gulf Stream path identified by the 25-cm SSH contour. The thin black dashed lines show isobaths at 100 m, 1000 m, and 4000 m depths. The yellow star is the location of Morehead City, NC. The blue diamonds denote drifter deployment locations. White boxes highlight **P3** and **P6** to indicate these are the stations where recovery of the PIES was not possible due to the position of the Gulf Stream.

September 1, 2024, and yearly thereafter until 2027, with the recovery of the CPIES planned for 2028 (Table 2). The auto-release date was set for Tuesday, April 16, 2030.

We slightly adjusted the originally planned **C2** site so that the PDS-PIES was close to the 1000 m isobath. We used the multibeam to determine the depth. During setup on the fantail prior to deployment, we noticed that the red light came on in each PDSs at 07:00 local. The PDS-PIES was in the water by 07:56. After deployment, we could communicate CLEAR commands and hear it sampling. We confirmed the instrument was on the bottom with the PIES Lab’s 8011M deckbox (SN 63369) and over-the-side transducer. This setup worked because the surface currents were very weak. After deploying the PDS-PIESs, we conducted a full water column CTD cast at **C2** (RR2407_cast_stationC2.hex). No water samples were taken (the bottles were removed from the rosette since we were not planning any water sampling on this cruise).

Thereafter, we transited to **P6**. We arrived at **P6** about 2 hours later. During the initial attempt at the CTD at this site, the wire jumped the shiv because the current was 4 knots, which was so strong that it swept the

package as soon as it hit the water. The wire got wedged, and it took some time for the ship's engineers to repair this issue. We finally started a full water column CTD cast (RR2407_cast_station_P6.hex) at 13:15 local, and the package was back aboard by 15:36. By that point, we had been swept ~1 mile from the **P6** site, so we steamed back to **P6**.

At **P6**, it was not possible to use the over-the-side transducer (it was immediately swept sideways by the currents), so we tried to use the ship's Universal Topside deckbox and 12-kHz through-hull transducer with TRAX9000 installed on the WHOI PIES LAB Dell computer and a USBA to USBC to serial cable for continuous transpond mode. Note that to make TRAX9000 work on the Dell, it was necessary to turn off Bluetooth on the Dell. Communication was very poor: we were unable to hear sample pings from **P6** (SN 446), and we were unable to hear replies to commands. We did have the ship's speed log and multibeam secured. Note that during deployment in January 2023 (on AR71, aboard R/V *Armstrong*), the currents were also very strong (with an estimated drift of 800 m as the CRIES fell through the water column). At that time, we were able to communicate with this PIES after deployment: we confirmed that it hit the bottom, we confirmed that it could hear and reply to CLEAR commands, and we confirmed that it was sampling. Finally, on RR2407 after, we sent a few "blind" RELEASE commands at 18:35, 18:36, and 18:39 local and waited for more than 1 hour. The ship did not hear the radio beacon on their RDF, and we do not think the PIES was released because it could not hear our commands. However, it is possible that **P6** did release, and we did not hear it; in that case, the Gulf Stream would have swept it downstream quickly.

We left **P6** without recovering the CRIES and skipped **P3** (where we anticipated that the currents would be just as strong). Instead, we transited north to **P5**. This station was still within the Gulf Stream but at the edge, so the speed was only about 1.5 knots. At 21:00 local, we conducted a full water column CTD at **P5** (RR2407_cast_stationp5.hex). After this, the students deployed three of the SIO drifters at **P5** (Figure 6).

Next, we recovered **P5** (SN 332 with CM 115). We used the 8011M deckbox, over-the-side transducer, and TRAX4 on the Toughbook to track the instrument's ascent. The instrument was on board by midnight. From **P5**, we transited west to **P2**.

Figure 6: Trajectory of SIO drifters deployed at **P5**.

On Saturday, June 8, 2024, we arrived at **P2** at 05:00 local and started a full water column CTD cast (RR2407_cast_stationP2.hex). The cast was complete by 06:15 local. We turned off the multibeam and speed log and established communications with the CPIES at **P2**, sitting directly over the site. Then, we had the captain reposition the ship (based on the expected rise location calculated using the HDSS velocity profiles and a small additional standoff). We sent the RELEASE command at 07:19 local using the 8011M deckbox and over-the-side transducer and had the **P2** CPIES (SN 304, CM 244) aboard by 08:05 local. We used the TRAX4 on the Toughbook to track the instrument's ascent.

We transited to **P4** and arrived at 08:50 local time, where we conducted a full water column CTD cast to a depth of approximately 1200m (RR2407_cast_stationp4.hex). Next, we tried to recover **P4** (SN 321; CM 112). During AR71, this instrument was listed as a "failed deployment" because when it was deployed, (1) the ocean was very noisy, with regular (instrument-like) noise, (2) we could not hear the instrument's sample pings after deployment, and (3) we could not get the instrument to reply to ACS commands after deployment. Note that the instrument behaved normally (including sampling on time) on deck before deployment. We tried to communicate with **P4** during RR2407, both during and after the CTD cast with the 8011M deckbox and

over-the-side transducer, but as expected, we could not hear the instrument sampling, and we were unable to get the instrument to reply to ACS CLEAR commands.

Nevertheless, we wanted to try a blind release. We first confirmed that the *Revelle's* RDF works by bringing a released instrument to the fan tail – using SN 447 (C1) as a test case. The RDF did work. We gave a series of 4 RELEASE commands using the 8011M and over-the-side transducer between 10:33 and 10:36 local. The instrument did not reply with the 4-ping response or give 6-second regular pings. We did note that the ocean was not as noisy as it was during deployment. Within the expected rise time (38-43 minutes), the instrument surfaced and was detected by the ship's RDF (one fun side-note: Magdalena simply did not believe Brian and Mason when they came through the lab and told her the instrument had surfaced and was heard by the RDF... but seeing is believing). The instrument was aboard by about noon. The instrument was not sampling, but the radio beacon and the strobe were functioning as expected. We connected the instrument to the Toughbook with the RS232 cable, and when we power cycled the instrument to reset the relay, the instrument gave its ping, and we were able to get to the menu. This instrument did not record acoustic travel time, but the bottom pressure, bottom temperature, and near-bottom current records are complete (Wang and Andres, 2024b). The instrument has been returned to the University of Rhode Island for assessment and repair before being redeployed (likely as part of the Aleutian Island IWR array to be deployed in July 2025). Next, we transited to C1. We arrived at 17:00 local for a PDS-PIES deployment of a CPIES (SN 447, CM 255) with PDS pods. We had trouble with one of the PDS pod setups, so we deployed this PDS-PIES with only 3 PDS pods (SN 164, 165, 167) and held onto SN 165 for evaluation. These three PDSs are set to surface on September 1, 2024, 2026, and 2027, respectively (Table 2). As with C2, the initial planned location was adjusted slightly to get as close as possible to the 1000 m isobath. The bridge transited west (onshore) and used the multibeam to identify the site. C1 was deployed at 13:30 local. Using the 8011M and over-the-side transducer and TRAX4 with the Toughbook, we could hear the instrument sampling on the descent, receive replies to CLEAR commands, and verify that the instrument was sampling on the bottom.

The **C1** instrument (analogous to **C2**) was set to sample round-trip vertical acoustic travel time (τ) with bursts of 16 12-kHz pings (alternating at 16 s and 18 s intervals) every 10 minutes and pressure and current measurements every 30 minutes. PDS pods are scheduled to launch on September 1, 2024, and yearly thereafter until 2027, with the recovery of the CPIES planned for 2028 (Table 2). The auto-release date was set for Tuesday, April 16, 2030.

After deploying **C1**, we conducted a full water column CTD cast (RR2407_cast_stationc1.hex) at this site. From there, we transited northeast to site **P1**.

We arrived at **P1** around 17:00 local and started a full water column CTD cast (RR2407_cast_stationp1.hex). After the cast, we recovered **P1** (SN 283, CM 43). The instrument surfaced at 19:00 local and was aboard by 19:15 local. Three drifters were deployed at this site (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Trajectory of SIO drifters deployed at **P1**.

After deploying the drifters, we steamed southeast to **P3** (which we had skipped earlier because it was expected to be in the Gulf Stream). We arrived at **P3** around 21:00 local, and the current was about 3.8 knots. We conducted a full water column CTD cast (RR2407_cast_stationp3.hex). After the cast, we tried communicating with the CPIES (SN 305, CM 113) using the ship's Universal Topside Deckbox and 12-kHz

transducer. As expected, this was unsuccessful; no communications were established. We decided not to release this instrument. This instrument's automatic release time is set for Saturday, May 17, 2025, at 12:00:00.

Figure 8: Instrument sites and SWOT Cal/Val swaths: **P1-P6** are MAB-SWOT CRIESs; **C1** and **C2** are Pioneer-adjacent PDS-PIES.

This final effort completed the PIES operations, and the cruise shifted to adaptive sampling during the transit home to Woods Hole. The adaptive sampling with XBTs began at ~07:00 local on Sunday, June 9, 2024, and continued during the transit through ~01:00 on Monday, June 10, 2024; see Section 4.1 for details. To prepare for the adaptive sampling, we had asked for the capability to deploy XBTs and eXpendable CTDs (xCTDs) during the pre-cruise meeting, and we arrived on the ship with one box of each (12 probes in each box). It turns out that the ship's acquisition system cannot accommodate xCTDs (we would need an MK21 Data Acquisition System). We are working with Brent De Vries to see if this can be addressed by the fall NESMA cruise in October, RR2412. For the present cruise, RR2407, Brent generously gave us a box of the ship's XBTs (12) to deploy 17 probes (all XBTs). Post-cruise note: on the subsequent NESMA cruise, RR2409, we were able to borrow a launch system from Jason Chaytor and Eric Moore at Woods Hole USGS (MK21 system), which was able to accommodate the xCTDs. If needed, we will use this system on RR2412.

3 CPIES

The instrument locations are shown in Figure 8 with associated information listed for the MAB-SWOT CPIESs (Table 1) and the Pioneer-adjacent PDS-PIES (Table 2). At each CPIES and PDS-PIES site, a full-water column CTD cast was conducted (Figures 9, 10), with information for these casts listed in Table 3.

3.1 MAB-SWOT/NGIW-IWR CPIESs

Inst. Site	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°W)	Avg. water depth (m)*
P1	36.2334	74.3662	2026.3
P2	35.9997	74.5339	1854.3
P3	36.0039	74.1969	
P4	36.0001	74.6728	1219.4
P5	36.0001	74.3671	2152.1
P6	35.7502	74.2832	

Table 1: MAB-SWOT CPIES coordinates and average bottom water depth. *Average depths calculated from the time-average pressure records with atmospheric pressure (10.13 dbar) subtracted. CPIESs **P3** and **P6** are still to be recovered and are nominally located at 2422 m and 2403 m, respectively, based on multibeam measurements taken during deployment.

3.2 Pioneer-adjacent PDS-PIESs

SITE	IES SN	CM SN	PDS SN	IMEI Number	PDS Popup Date	ACS CODES				Deployment Site			Dplymt. Date	Auto Release Date
						T	X	B	R	Latitude	Longitude	Depth (m)		
C1	447	255				67	71	75	63	36° 03.125' N	74° 42.365' W	1004	8-Jun-24	Tuesday April 16, 2030 1200
			164	300534064510010	1-Sep-24									
			165	300534064511010	1-Sep-25									
			166	300534064511040	--									
			167	300534064513030	1-Sep-27									
C2	462	270				67	71	75	14	35° 42.005' N	74° 46.209' W	1029	7-Jun, 2024	Tuesday April 16, 2030 1200
			168	300534064515020	1-Sep-24									
			169	300534064515030	1-Sep-25									
			170	300534064516030	1-Sep-26									
			171	300534064517010	1-Sep-27									

PDS 166 was not deployed

Depth is from multibeam at deployment

Table 2: Information for Pioneer-adjacent PIESs and their PDS pods.

3.3 Calibration CTDs at the CPIESs Sites

Site	Calibration CTD filename	Date	Latitude	Longitude	Depth (m)
P1	RR2407_cast_stationP1.hex	8-Jun-24	36°14.066' N	74°21.869' W	2030
P2	RR2407_cast_stationP2.hex	8-Jun-24	35°59.981' N	74°32.041' W	1867
P3	RR2407_cast_stationP3.hex	9-Jun-24	36°00.800' N	74°11.253' W	2546
P4	RR2407_cast_stationP4.hex	8-Jun-24	36°00.021' N	74°40.435' W	1128
P5	RR2407_cast_stationP5.hex	8-Jun-24	36°00.002' N	74°21.950' W	2178
P6	RR2407_cast_stationP6.hex	7-Jun-24	35°45.431' N	74°16.581' W	2424
C1	RR2407_cast_stationC1.hex	8-Jun-24	36°03.118' N	74°42.386' W	1000
C2	RR2407_cast_stationC2.hex	7-Jun-24	35°42.002' N	74°46.213' W	1024

Table 3: Summary of calibration CTD casts.

4 Adaptive Sampling

Before the cruise, the adaptive sampling team (Gawarkiewicz, Perez, and Enders) reviewed an image of sea surface temperature from June 5, 2024, of the Northeast region from Rutgers' [RU-COOL Satellite Imagery site](#). The team identified a Gulf Stream shingle as a region of interest for sampling (Figure 11). The New England Shelf and Slope south of Woods Hole was also highlighted as a region of interest due to dynamic processes that occur over that region. Prior observations in this area indicated anomalously cold and fresh conditions (Record et al., 2024). An important aspect of the cruise was communicating the oceanographic conditions to the Squid Squad, an informal group that includes commercial fishing industry representatives.

The adaptive sampling was focused on two primary features. The first was a large Gulf Stream shingle east of New Jersey, formed from a large, quasi-stationary Gulf Stream meander crest. These features have not been investigated for some time in the scientific literature. The second was the Shelfbreak Front, which was used to determine the frontal structure and the Cold Pool temperature. The Cold Pool bottom temperature is important to the commercial fishing industry, and this information was also communicated to the commercial fishing industry in Rhode Island.

While on station at P3 at 20:00 local time on June 8, 2024, the adaptive sampling team created a sampling plan for the Gulf Stream shingle. The adaptive sampling would begin at 05:00 local time on June 9, 2024, and end on June 10, 2024, at 23:00 since the *Revelle* was scheduled to be in port on June 11, 2024. Therefore, the

Figure 9: CTD casts at stations (a) C2, (b) P6, (c) P5, and (d) P2. Temperature [°C] (blue) and salinity [PSU] (orange) are plotted against pressure [dbar]. The blue bottom x-axes show temperature, and the orange top x-axes show salinity ranges.

adaptive sampling team had 43 hours of ship time, while accounting for the 5-hour breaks between the end of Watch B and Watch A, as well as accounting for the time to generally transit towards the shelf just south of Woods Hole, where science operations will end and the steam into port begins. After the rest of the science operations and transit time, there were about 35 hours left for the adaptive sampling operations.

Figure 10: CTD casts at stations (a) **P4**, (b) **C1**, (c) **P1**, and (d) **P3**. Temperature [°C] (blue) and salinity [PSU] (orange) are plotted against pressure [dbar]. The blue bottom x-axes show temperature, and the orange top x-axes show salinity ranges.

The adaptive sampling team split the plan into two parts: i) sample the shingle while moving along-stream just north of the Gulf Stream and ii) sample across the New England Shelf. The first and last shelf stations were chosen to bisect the shingle, and 15 stations were linearly spaced about 7 nautical miles apart between the ends for a total of 17 Shingle Stations (SS), **SS01–SS17** (Figure 12). It was determined that to save time, XBTs would

Figure 11: 6-hour composite of the Northwest Atlantic sea surface temperatures from Cape Hatteras to Nova Scotia on June 5, 2024. The black box highlights the Gulf Stream shingle. Figure courtesy of Rutgers' Department of Marine and Coastal Sciences and University of Delaware ORB Labs.

primarily be deployed at each station, with three full-column CTD casts at **SS06** (RR2407_cast_stationSS6.hex), **SS09** (RR2407_cast_stationSS9.hex), and **SS12** (RR2407_cast_stationSS12.hex). The three CTD profiles were sampled to investigate the salinity structure within the core of the shingle. Three drifters— two directional wave spectra barometer drifters (DWSBD) and one surface velocity program drifter (SVPD) were deployed (Figure 13). The DWSBDs are without drogues and are primarily moved by winds and surface waves. The SVPDs have a drogue at 15 m and are more influenced by subsurface currents at 15 m depth.

For the New England Shelf, nine stations were chosen to span 71 °W from approximately the bottom of the shelf's slope at the 2000-m isobath to the middle of the continental shelf (Figure 16). The first three stations, **NESS01–NESS03**, were linearly spaced about 10 nautical miles apart, and stations **NESS04** and **NESS05** were spaced about 5 nautical miles apart. The team decided to perform CTD casts at all stations because the water column was shallower over this region, and each cast would take about 1-1.5 hours for **NESS01–NESS03** and

Figure 12: Map of the Shingle Stations (SS). Inverted purple triangles denote locations of the XBT deployments, CTD casts by yellow Xs, and drifter deployments by blue diamonds. Color shading is SSH from absolute dynamic topography. The thick black line is the Gulf Stream path identified by the 25-cm SSH contour. The thin black dashed lines show isobaths at 1000-m and 4000-m depth. Planned deployment locations and actual deployment locations were approximately the same. See the eLog at the end of the document for exact locations.

Drifter Type (SVPD with drogue or DWSBD "wave drifter")	Drifter ID (Box)	Drifter ID (Web)	Latitude	Longitude	Date/ Time (GMT)	Notes (station/feature deployed in)
SVPD	64035960	7810311	36 00.025 N	074 21.921 W	06-07-2024 2:38:00 AM	Station P5
DWSBD	64132000	7810318	36 00.025 N	074 21.921 W	06-07-2024 2:38:10 AM	Station P5
DWSBD	64132120	7810315	36 00.025 N	074 21.921 W	06-07-2024 2:38:15 AM	Station P5
SVPD	64035970	7810312	36 13.739 N	074 S21.376 W	06-08-2024 11:20:26 PM	Station P1
DWSBD	64132110	7810317	36 13.739 N	074 21.376 W	06-08-2024 11:20:26 PM	Station P1
DWSBD	64132880	7810321	36 13.739 N	074 21.376 W	06-08-2024 11:20:26 PM	Station P1
SVPD	64036970	7810313	38 30.744 N	072 15.354 W	06-09-2024 11:40:00 PM	Shingle Station 12
DWSBD	64132020	7810320	38 30.744 N	072 15.354 W	06-09-2024 11:40:00 PM	Shingle Station 12
DWSBD	64132270	7810316	38 30.744 N	072 15.354 W	06-09-2024 11:40:00 PM	Shingle Station 12
SVPD	64034990	7810310	38 32.984 N	072 14.839 W	06-10-2024 2:29:00 PM	NESS 02
DWSBD	64132140	7810319	38 32.984 N	072 14.839 W	06-10-2024 2:29:00 PM	NESS 02
DWSBD	64131890	7810314	40 05.007 N	071 00.054 W	06-10-2024 8:14:58 PM	NESS 05

Table 4: Summary of drifter deployments.

about 0.5 hours for **NESS04–NESS09**. Drifters were deployed at **NESS02** (one DWSBD and one SVPD, with drogue) and **NESS05** (one DWSBD).

Drifters Deployed on New England Shelf [38 32.984° N, 072 14.839° W]
Deployed on June-08-2024

Figure 13: Trajectory of SIO drifters deployed at **SS12**.

4.1 Gulf Stream Shingle

After **P3**, the ship began the 105 nautical mile transit to the first station, **SS01**, located at 37°30' N, 73°2.52' W. Originally, we estimated the transit to take 10.5 hours; however, once the ship moved off the station around 23:00 local, the ETA to **SS01** was 6.5 hours, due to the current moving the ship along stream faster than anticipated. After the adaptive sampling began, we decided to have the bridge reduce the ship speed to 7 knots since we were ahead of schedule, and a slower transit speed would increase the data quality of the ADCP data.

At **SS01**, Brent De Vries deployed the first XBT at 07:04 local on June 9, 2024, to show Elena (Watch A lead) and Lilli (Watch B lead) how to teach their Watches the deployment steps. The bridge was radioed for each deployment for permission, and the bridge did not reduce ship speed for XBT deployments. Due to the mix-up about the ship's capabilities to deploy xCTDs, Brent gave the adaptive sampling team a box of the ship's Deep Blue XBT probes (in addition to the box of XBTs that Magdalena purchased).

Figure 14: Shingle Stations (SS) and New England Shelf Stations (NESS) CTD casts at (a) **SS06**, (b) **SS09**, (c) **SS12**, and (d) **NESS01**. Temperature [°C] (blue) and salinity [PSU] (orange) are plotted against pressure [dbar]. The blue bottom x-axes show temperature, and the orange top x-axes show salinity ranges.

With stations evenly spaced about 7 nautical miles apart and ship speed averaging 7 knots, XBTs were deployed about every 45–55 minutes starting at 07:04 local at **SS01** to **SS05** at 10:51. The XBTs would be deployed off the starboard side of the stern. The wire was snapped to stop recording at approximately 1000

m depth for all deployments. The initial XBT probes for many stations **SS02–SS17** failed, and a second probe was deployed when the initial one failed. It was unclear why the probes were initially failing, but we could record the XBT profile on the second attempt with no issue.

We arrived at **SS06**, 38°0' N, 72°39.39' W, at 11:45 local and stopped at the station. No XBT was deployed because we performed a CTD cast to about 300 m depth to capture the upper layer of the shingle (Figure 14a). The CTD cast took about 45 minutes. After the CTD cast, we continued to **SS07** for an XBT deployment at 13:23 local and then **SS08** for an XBT deployment at 14:24 local time. We stopped on **SS09** for another CTD cast to 300-m depth, which started at 14:54 and took about 45 minutes (Figure 14b). We had two more XBT deployments at **SS10** and **SS11** at 16:09 and 17:03, respectively, before the last CTD cast of the shingle stations at **SS12**, located at 38 °30.744' N, 72 °15.354' W. The CTD cast at **SS12** started at 17:57 local and took about 35 minutes (Figure 14c). The rear port bow thruster had some issues retracting as we attempted to leave **SS12**. Drifter deployments were delayed about 1.5 hours while waiting for the engineers to fix the problem. The issue with the bow thruster was resolved at 19:45 local. As we left **SS12**, three drifters were deployed off the stern at approximately 19:45. Of the three drifters, two DWSBD (#7810320 and #7810316) and one SVPD (#7810313) were deployed (Figure 13).

We began XBT deployments again every 45–55 minutes from **SS13** at 20:34 local. Glen requested a two-hour pause on **SS14** for squid watch, but due to the issue with the bow thruster on **SS12**, the bridge could only allow a 30-minute pause on **SS14**. The ship held its position on **SS12** from about 21:30 to 22:00 local, while various science party members and some crew attempted to catch squid with makeshift squid jigs, courtesy of Res. Tech Mason. At 22:30, we left **SS14** for the last three stations, **SS15–SS17**, and deployed XBTs about 55 minutes apart at 22:55 on June 9, 2024, 23:45 on June 9, 2024, and 00:40 local on June 10, 2024, respectively. The last XBT deployment at **SS17** concluded the first day of the adaptive sampling plan and the end of the shingle sampling (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Summary of data acquired from XBT deployments. Thin black lines represent individual XBT casts, thick lines (orange, blue, pink) represent the mean of all profiles, and shaded regions represent one standard deviation from the mean. (A) Resistance, (B) sound speed, and (C) temperature.

4.2 New England Shelf

After completing the shingle sampling, we focused on the secondary objective of our adaptive sampling regime: the New England Shelf. We designated 9 New England Shelf Stations (NESS) to collect data from CTD casts (Figures 14d, 17, 18). These stations followed a trajectory of approximately 71°W and were evenly spaced around the climatological position of the Shelfbreak Jet centre at a latitude of 40°10' N. After departing from our final Shingle Station (SS17), we began transit to the first Shelf Station (**NESS01**). We maintained a speed of 7 knots during this transit to ensure the quality of underway ADCP data collection.

We arrived at **NESS01** on the morning of June 10, 2024, and began our first CTD cast of the day at 06:45 local time (Figure 14d). The depth of this cast was capped at 1000 m, a depth selected to resolve the near-surface features of the site while remaining conscientious of our limited time (total cast time for 1000 m is approximately 1.5 hours). We then continued to the next shelf station, **NESS02**, located 10 nautical miles due North of **NESS01**, where we performed another CTD cast to a depth of 1000 m (Figure 17a).

We repeated this process for the remaining shelf stations, performing a CTD cast at each station before transiting to the next waypoint. The first four stations, **NESS01–NESS04**

(RR2407_cast_stationNESS01–04.hex), were located 10 nautical miles apart, along the 71 °W line, which

Figure 16: Map of the New England Shelf Stations (NESS). Locations of planned CTD casts are denoted by yellow Xs and planned drifter deployments by blue diamonds, with station labels highlighted in light blue for drifter stations. Color shading is SSH from absolute dynamic topography. The magenta star is the location of Woods Hole, MA. The thin black dashed lines show isobaths at 100-m and 1000-m depth. Planned deployment locations and actual deployment locations were approximately the same. See the eLog at the end of the document for exact locations.

resulted in a transit time of approximately 1.5 hours. The remainder of the stations, **NESS04-NESS09** (RR2407_cast_stationNESS04–09.hex), were more closely spaced, only 5 nautical miles apart (approximately 45 minutes at 7 knots). For sites where water depth exceeded 1000 m, we limited the depth of our casts to 1000 m (this was the case for **NESS01-NESS03**). For sites where the water depth was less than 1000 m, the CTD casts covered the full extent of the water column, stopping 5-10 m above the seabed (the exact stopping depth was dependent on conditions and bridge approval). Water depth steadily decreased as we continued north along 71 °W. Our shallowest cast, at **NESS09** (40 °25' N, 71°0' W), reached a depth of only about 75 m. Upon Glen's request, we deployed our remaining three drifters along the New England shelf. At **NESS02** (39°40' N, 71°0' W), at approximately 10:30 local on June 10, 2024, we deployed one DWSBD (#7810319) and

Figure 17: New England Shelf Stations (NESS) CTD casts at (a) **NESS02**, (b) **NESS03**, (c) **NESS04**, and (d) **NESS05**. Temperature [°C] (blue) and salinity [PSU] (orange) are plotted against pressure [dbar]. The blue bottom x-axes show temperature, and the orange top x-axes show salinity ranges.

one SVPD (#7810310), continuing our protocol of deploying off the stern of the vessel as we were leaving station (Figure 19). At **NESS05** (40°00'54" N, 71°00'05" W), at approximately 20:15 local time, we deployed our final drifter, a DWSBD (#7810314) (Figure 20).

Figure 18: New England Shelf Stations (NESS) CTD casts at (a) **NESS06**, (b) **NESS07**, (c) **NESS08**, and (d) **NESS09**. Temperature [°C] (blue) and salinity [PSU] (orange) are plotted against pressure [dbar]. The blue bottom x-axes show temperature, and the orange top x-axes show salinity ranges.

We completed our final science operation, a CTD cast at **NESS09** (40°25' N, 71°0' W) at 21:15 local on the evening of June 10, 2024. Because we could not hold the station for the squid watch for as long as we had hoped on the previous evening, we decided to conduct another squid watch along the shelf with the students from UMass Dartmouth and Res. Tech Mason led the charge, and we observed squid as a group from 21:15

Drifters Deployed on New England Shelf [38 32.984° N, 072 14.839° W]
June-10-2024

Figure 19: Trajectory of SIO drifters deployed at New England Shelf station (NESS) 2

Drifters Deployed on New England Shelf [40 05.007° N, 071 00.054° W]
Deployed on June-10-2024

Figure 20: Trajectory of SIO drifter deployed at New England Shelf station (NESS) 9

until 23:15 local time. We held station at **NESS09** for the night before preparing to return to port in Woods Hole the following morning.

5 UHDAS/Velocity

The University of Hawaii Data Acquisition System (UHDAS) collects the shipboard RDI ADCP data and, along with ancillary feeds (heading and position), performs automated preliminary processing to provide data and figures to scientists onboard *Revelle* and other University-National Oceanographic Laboratory System (UNOLS) vessels. UHDAS Team members scrutinize daily automated e-mails sent out by each UHDAS computer to ensure that everything works well on each ship. The Joint Archive for Shipboard ADCP (JASADCP) is a Data Accession Center for post-processed, science-ready shipboard ADCP data supported by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA).

Figure 21: A time series of OS150NB velocities and backscatter June 7-10, 2024. CTD stations are noted with vertical lines.

Two UHDAS team members (Jules Hummon and James Ash) and the JASADCP liaison (Ayesha Genz) joined RR2407 for training on UHDAS in a "live" setting. The *Revelle* currently has a 150kHz RDI ADCP (OS150), which is functioning well. Data were collected using narrowband mode (NB) for the entire cruise (Figure 21). OS150NB range was about 250 m in the Gulf Stream and up to 400 m in Slope water due to different scattering conditions. After C/PIESs deployments and recoveries, the ship spent time surveying a shallow feature ("shingle") north of an anticyclonic Gulf Stream meander, where water is ejected to the north (Figure

22). As we approached that area, OS150 broadband mode was also enabled, with 2-m bins, to try and capture shallow features. The OS150 can ping with both BB and NB modes, alternating between each type of ping. Adding BB mode steals pings from NB mode but provides a different resolution, sometimes enabling smaller features to be identified. The ship slowed when OS150BB was enabled (to ~ 8 knots) to allow better spatial sampling of the region.

Figure 22: A zoomed-in time series of a subsurface eddy found just before we started the "shingle" surveys

Ayesha reprocessed the single-ping ADCP data daily and edited out bad points for OS150BB and OS150NB. OS150BB was reprocessed with 5-minute averages to increase the number of pings in the averages due to the small bin size (2 m). The velocity section for the full cruise track is shown in Figure 21 with a zoomed-in portion of the section shown in Figure 22 to highlight a subsurface feature.

6 Outreach

6.1 JP Students Leadership Training

Two graduate students from the MIT-WHOI JP were given the roles of Watch Leads for the two shifts. Elena Perez, a 4th year PhD student, was responsible for Watch A, and Lilli Enders, a 3rd year PhD student, was responsible for Watch B. Responsibilities of the Watch Leads include managing a 4-person shift, overseeing science operations, training the watch-standers on various science operations, such as CTD, XBT, and drifter

deployments, creating a plan of the day, communicating the science plan with the Chief, co-Chief Scientists, and the bridge, and being the liaison between the science party and bridge during the adaptive sampling science operations. In addition, the Watch Leaders mentored the undergraduates on plotting oceanographic data, logging observations, deploying instruments, and communicating with the crew over the radio.

6.2 UMass Blue Economy Students

The UMass Dartmouth Internship Program at WHOI offers a research opportunity for students without off-campus research experiences. Over the course of the program, from January to April 2024, students attend short courses in January and then work on a research project co-advised by a WHOI scientist and UMass Dartmouth faculty member for the rest of the spring semester. This program aims to introduce students to lab-based research opportunities and graduate studies in ocean sciences. The four students who participated in the program this year, Nicholas Carvalho, Annette Limoges, Zachary Pereira, and Jessica Smith, were invited to the science party of cruise RR2407.

“ I enjoyed my stay aboard the *Revelle* and am now certain that I would like to pursue a career in research

”

Nicholas Carvalho, UMass Dartmouth Blue Economy student

All students were introduced to basic observational oceanography methods on this cruise. The student's responsibilities on their watches included CTD casts, drifter deployments, XBT deployments, logging marine mammal observations, and noting interesting oceanographic features in the underway data. Beyond the responsibilities during their watches, the students were mentored in the operations that interested them most. Annette oversaw drifter deployments, including prepping the drifters, logging the deployments, and tracking their movements on the drifter website (courtesy of Martha Schönau, SIO). Jessica enthusiastically took charge of the marine mammal log, diligently watching for mammals from the bow for hours, noting each observation in the log book, and later identifying the mammals with the animals of the North Atlantic

book provided by Glen. Nicholas and Zachary were interested in improving their coding and plotting skills in oceanographic data. Nicholas made near-real-time maps of sea surface temperature and SSH data of the cruise region and plotted the waypoints, planned CTD casts, and deployments for the adaptive sampling team. Zachary worked with the underway data and made plots of thermosalinograph data (Figure 23). Elena mentored Nicholas and Zachary with these projects, providing them with some code and helping them add their code to improve their plots and figures. Both Nicholas and Zachary helped the adaptive sampling team estimate the duration of the science operations– which was much appreciated during the late-night planning sessions when the team’s ability to do math decreased exponentially.

Figure 23: Underway thermosalinograph data from the entire cruise. Temperature is plotted in panel (a), and salinity is plotted in panel (b). *Figure courtesy of Z. Pereira*

All four students presented at one of the daily science meetings in the main lab (Figure 25). Annette updated the science party on drifter deployments. Jessica updated the group on marine mammal observations (with pictures!). Nicholas showed the adaptive sampling plan figures, with proposed deployments marked on the maps. Zachary showed plots of the thermosalinograph data for the first four days of the cruise. The students also gave an end-of-cruise presentation on their experiences in the Blue Economy program and their first

oceanographic cruise. All of them had many positive experiences to share! Below, each student shares a summary of their cruise experience.

6.2.1 Nicholas Carvalho

Occasionally, you get to observe science outside of a classroom, and it is certainly a spectacle to see in practice. Thankfully, I had such an opportunity aboard the *Roger Revelle* for almost a week-long research cruise thanks to the generosity of Magdalena Andres, chief scientist. Aboard the *Revelle*, I was treated to many amenities, such as a ping-pong table and onboard gym, not to mention the excellent food. As part of my scientific responsibilities, I operated several CTD casts (on the lab end) and assisted in preparing and cleaning several of the sensors on the CTD. I also deployed several drifters and an XBT, which were all quite enjoyable to deploy. Coding has never been a strong suit of mine, but I was able to write some Python notebooks and improve upon my coding skills using real-time data, which made coding much more engaging. Whether it was enjoying dolphins riding the ship's wake, watching hopefully for schools of squid, or playing the tensest games of ping-pong, I enjoyed my stay aboard the *Revelle* and am now certain that I would like to pursue a career in research even if it may not be exactly ocean related.

“ I gained valuable skills using a variety of instruments to survey the physical characteristics of the water column from the surface to the deep sea.

”

Jessica Smith, UMass Dartmouth Blue Economy student

6.2.2 Annette Limoges

On the cruise, I helped out with sensor deployments. I assisted with XBT, CTD, and my favorite, the drifter deployments. The drifters can have different sensors; the ones we released measured wave height, temperature, and GPS location. When we throw them overboard, they are in boxes, so it looks like we are dumping packages in the ocean! It was really interesting to see how each drifter moved with the current over time.

When I was not helping with science, I was outside searching for marine mammals. On the Gulf In the stream, we saw many dolphins; they could often be seen playing in the bow wake. When we got further north, we mostly saw whales. Throughout the cruise, we also searched for squid. We left lights on the back of the boat at night to try and attract them. We started seeing them after leaving the Gulf Stream. One night, there were so many you could see them on the multibeam sonar, but we couldn't catch a single one! Among the squid, I also spotted a Mola Mola.

On clear nights, many of us would go to the front of the boat to look at the stars. If you are far enough off the coast, there is very little light pollution, so you can see tons of stars and the Milky Way galaxy.

“ Departing the R/V *Roger Revelle*, I carry with me not only technical proficiency and scientific knowledge but also a deep-seated gratitude for the privilege of exploring our planet's oceans alongside such passionate collaborators.

”

Zachary Pereira, UMass Dartmouth Blue Economy student

6.2.3 Zachary Pereira

Stepping aboard the R/V *Roger Revelle* was a transformative experience, blending nerves with excitement as I committed to a journey into the unknown depths of the Atlantic Ocean. Supported by a community of kindred spirits of crew and scientists, I quickly immersed myself in a whirlwind of scientific operations and discovery. From piloting the A-frame for equipment deployments to mastering the intricacies of CTD operations and analyzing real-time oceanographic data, every moment challenged me to grow professionally and personally. The thrill of assisting in a glider retrieval and aiding in the deployment of seafloor devices highlighted the practical applications of my classroom studies, cementing my role as a hands-on contributor to cutting-edge research. Beyond the science, I found solace in quiet moments on the ship's bow, engrossed in maritime literature from the ship's library and captivated by marine life sightings.

Each day brought new insights and skills, calculating trajectory times, coordinating operations with the ship's crew, and contributing to scientific briefings. As I navigated through sunrise operations and midnight discussions under the starlit sky, I realized the profound impact of this journey on my perspective and aspirations. The camaraderie shared over Bananagrams and dinners, the breathtaking sights of dolphin races at sunset, and the profound serenity of the Milky Way above the open sea—all these moments enriched my understanding of both the physical processes of the ocean and the power of human connection when navigating through challenges that initially seemed insurmountable. Departing the R/V *Roger Revelle*, I carry with me not only technical proficiency and scientific knowledge but also a deep-seated gratitude for the privilege of exploring our planet's oceans alongside such passionate collaborators. This experience has undoubtedly prepared me for a future dedicated to advancing oceanographic research and fostering innovative solutions to the challenges that lie ahead for our planet.

Figure 24: UMass Blue Economy student Jessica Smith cleaning the CTD rosette after recovery. Photo credit: Susie Crowe

6.2.4 Jessica Smith

The Blue Economy Internship allowed me to explore a vast spectrum of interdisciplinary oceanographic research. Participating in RR2407 with the physical oceanography department aboard R/V *Roger Revelle* gave me the opportunity to gain five days of hands-on experience at sea. I gained valuable skills using a variety of instruments to survey the physical characteristics of the water column from the surface to the deep sea. The instrument I became most familiar with was the CTD (Figure 24), used to measure conductivity, temperature, and depth via pressure. My favorite part about being at sea was observing all the wildlife and natural phenomena! From marine mammals to bioluminescent plankton, it is amazing to witness the biology that inhabits the vast expanse of the open ocean. RR2407 was a great experience, and I enjoyed learning more about Gulf Stream circulation alongside an amazing team of scientists and crew.

Figure 25: UMass Blue Economy students presenting at the daily science brief.

6.3 Careers Paths in Marine Sciences and Operations

Each afternoon, a different member of the Science Party was asked to give an informal presentation during the daily science brief to share with the JP graduate and UMass undergraduate students the many career paths available in marine operations and marine sciences. In addition to the "traditional" cruise participants from

the academic institutions (WHOI, University of Massachusetts Dartmouth, and the University of Hawaii), the Science Party included participants presently engaged in a wide range of marine science-related careers who discussed some "non-traditional" career paths. These included presentations by SIO Research Vessel Coordinator Hannah Delapp, an RBR sales representative, Susie Crow, a marine archaeologist and technician from the Coastal Studies Institute, Lindsay Wentzle, and a data manager from NOAA IRC, Ayesha Genz. In addition, members of the crew (John Clifford, Chief Engineer, and Pam Switzer, Chief Mate) gave presentations and tours of the engine room and bridge with a focus on the career paths available within the academic research fleet.

Upon RR2407's arrival in Woods Hole, the Captain, Chief Engineer, and Res Techs (Tom Desjardins, John Clifford, Mason Schetigg, and Noah DesRosiers) discussed life at sea and marine careers with several groups of undergraduates. They gave tours to WHOI's [Summer Student Fellows](#), sponsored by the NSF Research Experiences for Undergraduates and to WHOI [summer interns](#) engaged in the Improving Minority Participation in Education and Training in the Underwater Sciences (IMPETUS) program supported by the [Black Girls Dive Foundation](#) and sponsored by ONR.

7 Acknowledgements

The Science Party thanks Captain Tom Desjardins and the entire crew of R/V *Roger Revelle* for a successful cruise, and we particularly appreciate their willingness to engage with the graduate and undergraduate students during the cruise and upon our arrival in Woods Hole. We greatly appreciate the support for science provided by the SIO Res Techs, Mason Schettig and Noah DesRosiers. They are wonderful teachers and incredibly patient. We are grateful to Instrument Tech Brent De Vries for his support for the networking, underway data acquisition, and expert XBT training. We also appreciate the shoreside support the SIO Ship Operations group provided in preparing for the cruise and *Revelle's* move to the North Atlantic for summer/fall 2024.

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9 Appendix

9.1 Cruise Participants

R/V *Revelle* Crew

Tom Desjardins	Captain
Pamela Switzer	Chief Mate
John Clifford	Chief Engineer

Science Party

Magdalena Andres	Chief Scientist, WHOI
Glen Gawarkiewicz	Co-Chief Scientist, WHOI
Elena Perez	Watch Lead, MIT/WHOI Joint Program PO
Lilli Enders	Watch Lead, MIT/WHOI Joint Program PO
Ysabel Wang	MIT/WHOI Joint Program PO
Will Harris	MIT/WHOI Joint Program AOSE
Brian Hogue	Technician, WHOI
Snehal Prabhu	Information Systems associate, WHOI
Jules Hummon	Univ. of Hawaii Currents Group
Jamie Ash	Univ. of Hawaii Currents Group
Ayesha Genz	NOAA/NCEI

Nicholas Carvalho	UMass Dartmouth Blue Economy student
Annette Limoges	UMass Dartmouth Blue Economy student
Zachary Pereira	UMass Dartmouth Blue Economy student
Jessica Smith	UMass Dartmouth Blue Economy student
Hannah Delapp	SIO, R/V coordinator
Lindsay Wentzel	Technician, East Carolina Univ., Coastal Studies Institute
Susie Crow	RBR Sales Representative
Mason Schettig	SIO, Res Tech
Noah DesRosiers	SIO, Res Tech
Brent De Vries	SIO, Instrument Tech

Science party photo with a special appearance by Captain Tom (center front) and Chief Engineer John (center back).

9.2 Other

Find the processed underway data on Rolling Deck To Repository's page for cruise RR2407: <https://www.rvdata.us/search/cruise/RR2407>.

Video animation of cruise science operations by Jamie Ash (UH Currents Group): <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1zQysPiTgEt3Acp5Xhan5c2m3HKE2omTQ/view?usp=sharing>.

Links from the text:

MAB-SWOT Campaign: <https://www.swot-adac.org/campaigns/mab-swot/>

SWOT satellite: <https://swot.jpl.nasa.gov/>

SWOT Adopt a Crossover Consortium: <https://www.swot-adac.org/>

Internal Wave Resolving (IWR) arrays: <https://nopp-giw.ucsd.edu/teams/waterhouse/>

NOPP Global Internal Waves: <https://nopp-giw.ucsd.edu/>

Blue Economy Program: <https://www.who.edu/what-we-do/educate/undergraduate-programs/university-of-massachusetts-dartmouth-internship-program/>

WHOI Glider Archive (ID 24406201): <https://gliders.who.edu/data/archive/24406201.html>

RU-COOL Satellite Imagery: <https://marine.rutgers.edu/cool/data/satellites/imagery/>

WHOI Summer Student Fellowship: <https://www.who.edu/what-we-do/educate/undergraduate-programs/summer-student-fellowship/>

Black Girls Dive x WHOI Summer Internship: <https://www.who.edu/press-room/news-release/black-girls-dive-foundation-launches-program-in-partnership-with-woods-hole-oceanographic-institution/>

Black Girls Dive Foundation: <https://blackgirlsdivefoundation.org/streams>

9.3 eLog

The eLog is appended to the end of this report.

9.4 Hotwashes

Hotwashes are appended to the end of this report.

Message ID	Date and Time (UTC)	Instrument	Action	Station	Latitude	Longitude	Author	Comment
1	Thu, Jun 6, 2024 at 20:37:20	Ship	startCruise	NaN	34.715717	-76.695945	sPrabh1	
2	Fri, Jun 7, 2024 at 10:16:35	Spray Glider	recover	NaN	35.70343	-74.732777	sPrabh1	
3	Fri, Jun 7, 2024 at 11:54:56	PIES	deploy	C2	35.700081	-74.769849	sPrabh1	
4	Fri, Jun 7, 2024 at 12:52:30	CTD911	deploy	C2	35.700066	-74.770236	sPrabh1	
5	Fri, Jun 7, 2024 at 13:18:08	CTD911	maxDepth	C2	35.700051	-74.770232	sPrabh1	
6	Fri, Jun 7, 2024 at 13:38:32	CTD911	recover	C2	35.700073	-74.770228	sPrabh1	
7	Fri, Jun 7, 2024 at 17:18:49	CTD911	deploy	P6	35.762037	-74.271253	sPrabh1	
8	Fri, Jun 7, 2024 at 18:24:48	CTD911	maxDepth	P6	35.796329	-74.234854	sPrabh1	
9	Fri, Jun 7, 2024 at 19:24:21	CTD911	recover	P6	35.82012	-74.208905	sPrabh1	
10	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 2:47:14	CTD911	deploy	P5	36.000679	-74.365116	IEnders	
12	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 2:48:34	CTD911	recover	P5	36.000558	-74.365233	IEnders	
13	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 2:53:06	DWS Drifter	deploy	P5	36.000512	-74.36531	IEnders	DWSBD 300534064132000
14	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 2:54:01	DWS Drifter	deploy	P5	36.0005	-74.365313	IEnders	DWSBD 300534064132120
15	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 2:54:29	SVP drifter	deploy	P5	36.000495	-74.365313	IEnders	SVPD 64035960
16	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 9:06:52	CTD911	deploy	P2	35.999674	-74.533972	sPrabh1	
17	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 9:23:02	CTD911	maxDepth	P5	36.000477	-74.365323	IEnders	
18	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 9:43:31	CTD911	maxDepth	P2	35.999667	-74.533955	sPrabh1	
19	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 10:18:05	CTD911	recover	P2	35.999679	-74.533988	sPrabh1	
20	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 10:54:40	PIES	recover	P5	36.000138	-74.490314	sPrabh1	
21	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 12:05:23	PIES	recover	P2	35.995793	-74.534471	sPrabh1	
22	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 13:00:04	CTD911	deploy	P4	36.000326	-74.673899	sPrabh1	
23	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 13:25:36	CTD911	maxDepth	P4	36.000228	-74.673835	sPrabh1	
24	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 13:48:15	CTD911	recover	P4	36.000392	-74.673924	sPrabh1	
25	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 15:15:24	PIES	recover	P4	36.000395	-74.674128	sPrabh1	
26	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 17:28:28	PIES	deploy	C1	36.05193	-74.706369	sPrabh1	
27	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 18:10:00	CTD911	deploy	C1	36.051845	-74.706445	sPrabh1	
28	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 18:33:47	CTD911	maxDepth	C1	36.051957	-74.706422	sPrabh1	
29	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 18:53:54	CTD911	recover	C1	36.051922	-74.706417	sPrabh1	
31	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 21:25:37	CTD911	maxDepth	P1	36.234388	-74.364795	IWentzel	
32	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 21:36:22	CTD911	deploy	P1	36.234653	-74.364544	IWentzel	
33	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 22:02:02	CTD911	recover	P1	36.233307	-74.366356	IWentzel	
34	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 23:21:56	SVP drifter	deploy	P1	36.227949	-74.354995	IWentzel	SVPD 64035970
35	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 23:22:07	DWS Drifter	deploy	P1	36.227836	-74.354847	IWentzel	DWSBD 300534064132110_64132110
36	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 23:22:11	DWS Drifter	deploy	P1	36.227784	-74.35478	IWentzel	DWSBD 300534064132880_64132880
37	Sat, Jun 8, 2024 at 23:22:34	PIES	recover	P1	36.231202	-74.361546	IWentzel	
38	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 1:04:28	CTD911	deploy	P3	36.014409	-74.186587	IWentzel	
39	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 2:01:02	CTD911	maxDepth	P3	36.035768	-74.165882	IWentzel	
40	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 2:55:41	CTD911	recover	P3	36.049737	-74.149173	IWentzel	
41	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 12:15:13	Sippican Fast-Deep XBT	release	Shingle_station_2	37.595628	-72.968801	sPrabh1	
42	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 12:16:09	Sippican Fast-Deep XBT	release	Shingle_station_1	37.498047	-73.045515	sPrabh1	
43	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 13:06:38	Sippican Fast-Deep XBT	release	Shingle_station_3	37.705855	-72.880979	sPrabh1	

44	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 14:05:28	Sippican Fast-Deep XBT	release	Shingle_station_4	37.804403	-72.80715	sPrabh1	
45	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 14:55:18	Sippican Fast-Deep XBT	release	Shingle_station_5	37.903188	-72.730745	sPrabh1	
46	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 15:02:19	Sippican Fast-Deep XBT	other	Shingle_station_5	37.899483	-72.732322	sPrabh1	Bad XBT aborted
47	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 16:04:29	CTD911	deploy	Shingle_station_6	38.001764	-72.652962	sPrabh1	
48	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 16:12:04	CTD911	maxDepth	Shingle_station_6	38.00532	-72.649862	sPrabh1	depth of 300m
49	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 16:19:39	CTD911	recover	Shingle_station_6	38.007191	-72.648233	sPrabh1	
50	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 17:22:07	Sippican Fast-Deep XBT	other	Shingle_station_7	38.097434	-72.580475	sPrabh1	Bad XBT aborted
51	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 17:26:20	Sippican Fast-Deep XBT	release	Shingle_station_7	38.104578	-72.574602	sPrabh1	
52	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 18:25:02	Sippican Fast-Deep XBT	release	Shingle_station_8	38.200912	-72.501076	sPrabh1	
53	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 19:09:13	CTD911	deploy	Shingle_station_9	38.249071	-72.462518	IWentzel	
54	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 19:13:58	CTD911	maxDepth	Shingle_station_9	38.249111	-72.462403	IWentzel	Depth of 300m
55	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 19:23:28	CTD911	recover	Shingle_station_9	38.249069	-72.462455	IWentzel	
56	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 20:00:19	Sippican Fast-Deep XBT	release	Shingle_station_10	38.300692	-72.42493	IWentzel	
57	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 21:00:42	Sippican Fast-Deep XBT	release	Shingle_station_11	38.399921	-72.3479	IWentzel	
58	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 22:09:23	CTD911	deploy	Shingle_Site_12	38.500606	-72.270054	IWentzel	
59	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 22:16:51	CTD911	maxDepth	Shingle_Site_12	38.50058	-72.270039	IWentzel	Depth of 300m
60	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 22:25:05	CTD911	recover	Shingle_station_12	38.500599	-72.270055	IWentzel	
61	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 23:40:41	SVP drifter	deploy	Shingle_station_12	38.511408	-72.256142	IWentzel	SVPD 300534064036970_64036970
63	Sun, Jun 9, 2024 at 23:41:10	DWS Drifter	deploy	Shingle_station_12	38.51209	-72.255969	IWentzel	DWSBD 300534064132020_64132020
64	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 0:28:30	Sippican Fast-Deep XBT	release	Shingle_station_13	38.603068	-72.235515	IWentzel	XBT Deep Blue used. All prior XBT = Fast, all following XBT = Deep Blue
65	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 1:17:04	Sippican Fast-Deep XBT	other	Shingle_station_14	38.702184	-72.200383	IWentzel	Bad XBT aborted
66	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 1:20:29	Sippican Fast-Deep XBT	release	Shingle_station_14	38.709055	-72.197762	IWentzel	
67	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 2:33:07	Sippican Fast-Deep XBT	release	Shingle_station_15	38.801181	-72.166385	IWentzel	
68	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 3:23:38	Sippican Fast-Deep XBT	release	Shingle_station_16	38.900288	-72.131139	IWentzel	
69	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 4:11:54	Sippican Fast-Deep XBT	release	Shingle_station_17	38.998825	-72.09557	IWentzel	
70	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 11:19:00	CTD911	deploy	NESS1	39.496597	-70.999629	IEnders	
71	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 11:32:43	CTD911	maxDepth	NESS1	39.496574	-70.999627	IEnders	
72	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 11:52:59	CTD911	recover	NESS1	39.496587	-70.999649	IEnders	
73	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 13:40:22	CTD911	deploy	NESS2	39.666465	-70.999407	sPrabh1	
74	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 14:00:04	CTD911	maxDepth	NESS2	39.666528	-70.999372	sPrabh1	1000 m
75	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 14:19:24	CTD911	recover	NESS2	39.666544	-70.999422	sPrabh1	
76	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 16:05:33	CTD911	deploy	NESS3	39.831594	-70.999068	sPrabh1	
77	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 16:24:21	CTD911	maxDepth	NESS3	39.83158	-70.999347	sPrabh1	
78	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 16:43:48	CTD911	recover	NESS3	39.831555	-70.999347	sPrabh1	
79	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 19:48:10	CTD911	deploy	NESS4	40.000404	-71.001994	IWentzel	
80	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 19:48:13	CTD911	maxDepth	NESS4	40.000404	-71.001994	IWentzel	
81	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 19:48:15	CTD911	recover	NESS4	40.000436	-71.002005	IWentzel	
82	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 19:55:07	CTD911	deploy	NESS5	40.083655	-71.000375	IWentzel	
83	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 20:02:21	CTD911	maxDepth	NESS5	40.083643	-71.000361	IWentzel	
84	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 20:08:29	CTD911	recover	NESS5	40.08363	-71.000287	IWentzel	

85	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 20:15:47	DWS Drifter	deploy	NESS5	40.083533	-71.001546	IWentzel	DWSBD 300534064131890_64131890
86	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 21:09:37	CTD911	deploy	NESS6	40.166368	-71.000489	IWentzel	
87	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 21:15:15	CTD911	maxDepth	NESS6	40.16634	-71.00051	IWentzel	
88	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 21:20:56	CTD911	recover	NESS6	40.166363	-71.000484	IWentzel	
89	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 22:19:53	CTD911	deploy	NESS7	40.250284	-71.000524	IWentzel	
90	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 22:23:01	CTD911	maxDepth	NESS7	40.250321	-71.000418	IWentzel	
91	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 22:27:17	CTD911	recover	NESS7	40.250292	-71.000474	IWentzel	
92	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 23:29:08	CTD911	deploy	NESS8	40.333708	-70.999886	IWentzel	
93	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 23:31:51	CTD911	maxDepth	NESS8	40.333685	-70.99991	IWentzel	
94	Mon, Jun 10, 2024 at 23:35:29	CTD911	recover	NESS8	40.333667	-70.999835	IWentzel	
95	Tue, Jun 11, 2024 at 0:55:35	CTD911	deploy	NESS9	40.46632	-71.001316	IWentzel	
96	Tue, Jun 11, 2024 at 0:59:40	CTD911	maxDepth	NESS9	40.466334	-71.001302	IWentzel	
97	Tue, Jun 11, 2024 at 1:03:10	CTD911	recover	NESS9	40.466314	-71.001363	IWentzel	
98	Tue, Jun 11, 2024 at 19:27:39	Ship	endCruise		41.523958	-70.67225	sPrabhu1	

RR2407 Hot Wash: Pioneer-Adjacent PIES Deployments

RAPID: A Cost-Effective Approach for Characterizing Variability at High Temporal Resolution for Long Duration on the Continental Slope of the Southern Mid-Atlantic Bight

Two popeye data shuttle-enabled current and pressure sensor equipped inverted echo sounders (PDS-PIESs, **Figure 1**) were successfully deployed on the continental slope east of the Ocean Observatories Initiative (OOI) Pioneer Array in the southern Mid Atlantic Bight in June 2024. Data collected during the 4-year deployments will be shared broadly when PDS pods ascend annually to the sea surface and return data batches via a satellite link.

Figure 1. MIT/WHOI Joint Program students, Ysabel Wang (right, Physical Oceanography) and Will Harris (left, Applied Ocean Science and Engineering) and WHOI technician Brian Hogue (background) preparing a PDS-PIES for deployment. The instrument will measure round trip vertical acoustic travel time with bursts of 16 pings every 10 minutes and near-bottom pressure and current measurements every 30 minutes. The PDSs (orange) are scheduled to rise to the sea surface to return data batches remotely on September 1 in 2024 and yearly thereafter until 2027 with recovery of the PIES (white) planned for 2028.

The scientific motivation is to (1) capture mesoscale variability offshore of the Pioneer Array, (2) capture western excursions of the Gulf Stream North Wall that may influence ocean-shelf exchange, and (3) observe the upper portion of the equatorward-flowing Deep Western Boundary Current where it squeezes under the poleward flowing Gulf Stream. The PDS-PIESs were deployed on the 1000 m isobath 40-km apart to extend the Pioneer Array mooring footprint offshore and to allow comparison with a glider which is running a line (nominally) along the 1000 m isobath (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2. Map of PDS-PIESs (red dots, C1: 36° 3.125' N; 74° 42.365' W and C2: 35° 42.005' N; 74° 46.209' W), Pioneer moorings (yellow dots), and nominal offshore Pioneer glider line (blue). Red curve is time-averaged position of the Gulf Stream core and dotted lines are Jason altimeter tracks. Heavy contours are the 200 and 1000 m isobaths.

Cruise RR2407 was supported through the Office of Naval Research through the National Ocean Partnership Program Global Internal Wave (NGIW) study and provided at sea experiences for 4 MIT/WHOI Joint Program students and 4 undergraduates from the University of Massachusetts Dartmouth as part of their Blue Economy Program with WHOI. Many thanks to the National Science Foundation Division of Ocean Sciences for funding the PDS-PIES deployments and to engineer Erran Sousa from the University of Rhode Island who provided emergency shoreside support (on a Saturday!) to walk us through the PDS setups.

RR2407 Hot Wash: MAB-SWOT Adopt-A-Crossover CPIEs Recoveries

¹NASA: “Surface Water Ocean Topography (SWOT) Adopt-A-Crossover field campaign - Cape Hatteras”

²ONR: “A Distributed Network of Internal Wave Resolving Moored Arrays for Assessing Tide-Resolving Model Fields and Improving Forecasts in the Coastal Ocean”

Cruise RR2407 departed from Morehead City, NC on June 6, 2024 and arrived in Woods Hole, MA on June 11, 2024. The Science Party aboard *RV Roger Revelle* successfully recovered 4 current and pressure sensor equipped inverted echo sounders (CPIEs) that were deployed for 18-months east of Cape Hatteras (**Figure 1**, left) and conducted full-water column CTD casts for calibrations at 6 sites (middle). In addition, the team recovered a Spray glider (right). The *in situ* instruments were part of an array deployed through the Mid-Atlantic Bight-Surface Water Ocean Topography (MAB-SWOT) project which “adopted” the SWOT crossover site east of Cape Hatteras: <https://www.swot-adac.org/campaigns/mab-swot/> (**Figure 2**) where there was a 90-day Cal/Val period with rapid sampling (twice per day) by the new NASA SWOT satellite (<https://swot.jpl.nasa.gov>). The project was endorsed by and falls under the umbrella of the SWOT Adopt a Crossover Consortium: <https://www.swot-adac.org/>. The effort also dovetails with a broader effort to obtain *in situ* measurements of internal waves globally (<https://nopp-giw.ucsd.edu/teams/waterhouse/>).

Figure 1. Science activities aboard RR2407. Left: Brian Hogue (WHOI) and Mason Schettig (UCSD) recovering a CPIEs. Middle: Watch B conducting a full water column CTD cast, left to right: Nick Carvalho (UMass Dartmouth), Lilli Enders (WHOI/MIT Joint Program), Lindsay Wentzel (CSI), Annette Limoges (UMass Dartmouth). Right: rescuing a glider for coPI Robert Todd. The glider had lost the ability to steer due to a broken tail fin a few days before the cruise. Photo credits: M. Andres (WHOI).

Measurements from the *in situ* instruments (CPIEs, gliders and a moored acoustic Doppler current profiler—together with measurements from several shore-based high-frequency (HF) radar installations—were collected along and offshore of the MAB for an 18-month period (January 2023-June 2024) that included the Cal/Val period of the SWOT satellite mission. The goals of the MAB-SWOT project are to:

- (1) advance the community’s dynamical understanding of the key oceanographic region east of Cape Hatteras where the Gulf Stream leaves the continental margin and crosses over the Deep Western Boundary Current and where there are vigorous shelf/ocean exchanges and complex sub-mesoscale dynamics associated with entrainment of shelf waters in the Gulf Stream North Wall;
- (2) validate measurements provided by the SWOT satellite mission; and

RR2407 Chief Sci.: Magdalena Andres | Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI)

¹WHOI subaward from U. North Carolina, Chapel Hill | NASA Ocean Physics Program prime |1687411

²WHOI subaward from U. of California San Diego | National Ocean Partnership Program (NOPP) Global Internal Wave (NGIW) study | ONR prime | N000142212575

(3) measure internal tides with Internal Wave Resolving Arrays deployed in multiple locations for a comprehensive comparison with output from global ocean general circulation models that include tidal forcing (<https://nopp-giw.ucsd.edu>).

Figure 2. Left: regional context for the US East Coast SWOT crossover and MAB-SWOT array. Right: CRIES sites (P1-P6), ADCP mooring, coastal HF radar locations and glider tracks from the MAB-SWOT array and tracks of three companion NRL Twin Otter flights during the Cal/Val period (yellow). Figures courtesy of coPI R. Todd (WHOI).

Despite the success of RR2407 and tremendous support by the *Revelle* crew and Res Techs, two of the PIES (P3 and P6) have not yet been recovered. *Revelle's* 12 kHz through-hull transducer has been out of commission for some time. The University of California San Diego (UCSD) Shipboard Technical Support team was not able to find a replacement transducer in time for RR2407 and the ship was not prepared to use the moon pool and pipe string (Figure 3) to affix the Science Party's 12 kHz dunking transducer. This—coupled with 4 knot currents at these two sites because of an unusually northward-shifted Gulf Stream during RR2407—made it impossible to communicate with these CRIESs. Since it was not possible to send a release command to the instruments, it will be necessary to revisit the sites with a better equipped ship before their automatic release date in April 2025. This could be done aboard *Revelle* (e.g., with an adaptor plate for the pipe string or by using a 700 lb pig weight to hold down an over-the side transducer and minimize kiting by the swift Gulf Stream). It may also be possible to capitalize on other ships' transits through the region (e.g., RVs *Neil Armstrong*, *Langseth*, *Endeavor* or *Atlantic Explorer*, which are all equipped with the necessary tools for successful CRIES recoveries in strong currents).

Figure 3. Left: disassembled pipe string (white pipes on left side of photo) and moon pool cover with hole (right side) that allow transducers and other gear to be lowered through the ship and flush or just past the bottom of the hull. Right: 700 lb. pig weight that could potentially be used to hold the over the side transducer (not an ideal solution, but could work in a pinch). Photo credits: M. Andres.

RR2407 Chief Sci.: Magdalena Andres | Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI)

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Next Steps: The data from the 4 recovered CPIESs (P1, P2, P4 and P4) are being processed to provide level 0-2 datasets (e.g., [Figure 4](#)) and a technical report that describes the processing steps to the community by June 30, 2024, which marks the end of the NASA-supported project. A full cruise report, describing these activities along with adjacent efforts on the cruise is being prepared and will be shared broadly when it is completed.

Figure 4. Preliminary plots of the hourly level 2 pressure and round-trip bottom-to-surface acoustic trave time data (τ) from P5 (SN 332). x-axis shows time in yearday since January 1, 2023.

The next step (beyond the scope of the NASA MAB-SWOT project, but within the scope of the National Ocean Partnership Program (NOPP) Global Internal Wave (NGIW) study) will be to create level 3 and 4 CPIES datasets and products and to conduct analysis to achieve goals 1-3 listed above. To help achieve these goals, funding is being sought to support an MIT/WHOI Joint Program graduate student, Ysabel Wang.

WHOI technician Brian Hogue is working with the *Revelle* Res Techs to design an adaptor plate for the pipe string and Magdalena Andres is working with the UCSD and WHOI ship schedulers to investigate which ships might be able to accommodate 12 to 18 hours of operations in the region before April 2025.

Acknowledgements and Funding: This project is funded by JPL/NASA through the Ocean Physics Program with a contract to the University of North Carolina Chapel Hill (UNC) and with subcontracts to the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI) and Coastal Studies Institute/East Carolina University (CSI). The lead PI is Harvey Seim (UNC) and co-PIs are Robert Todd and Magdalena Andres (WHOI), and Mike Muglia (CSI). The deployment cruise in January 2023 aboard *RV Neil Armstrong* (AR71) was part of a Woods Hole, MA to Pensacola, FL transit with NASA providing funding for a ship day to deploy the 6 CPIESs and conduct full-water column CTD casts at the study site. The recovery cruise in June 2024 aboard *RV Roger Revelle* (RR2407) was embedded in a transit to Woods Hole, MA (that marks the beginning of 6 months of work for *Revelle* in the Atlantic as part of the ONR Task Force Ocean New England Seamounts Acoustics Experiment) with two ship days for the science objectives funded by ONR through the NGIW program. The purchase of the CPIES instruments was made possible through an ONR Defense University Research Instrumentation Program (DURIP) award (N000142212209) to WHOI with the instrument batteries and other expendables supported by NASA. NASA support also funded all cruise related expenses (salary, travel, shipping) and salary for data processing (Level 0-2) and data dissemination.

RR2407 Chief Sci.: Magdalena Andres | Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI)

¹WHOI subaward from U. North Carolina, Chapel Hill | NASA Ocean Physics Program prime |1687411

²WHOI subaward from U. of California San Diego | National Ocean Partnership Program (NOPP) Global Internal Wave (NGIW) study | ONR prime | N000142212575

We are grateful to the *Revelle* crew and Captain Tom Desjardin and Chief Engineer John Clifford for an extremely productive cruise. We thank the Res Techs Mason Schettig and Noah DesRosier, for their support during the cruise, their assistance training the students, and for putting up with a deluge of ship tours during the cruise and upon arrival in Woods Hole.

Outreach and Synergies: RR2407 provided at-sea experiences for 4 MIT/WHOI Joint Program students and 4 undergraduates from the University of Massachusetts Dartmouth as part of their Blue Economy Program with WHOI and provided at-sea training for a new CSI technician, Lindsay Wentzel, from the lab of coPI Mike Muglia. (The earlier deployment cruise (AR71) provided the opportunity for a graduate student, Yubeen Jeong, from the lab of PI Harvey Seim to go to sea).

To fully capitalize on the space and capabilities of *Revelle* and make use of the 40-hour transit from the study site to Woods Hole, the students deployed drifters and XBTs and conducted adaptive sampling through a Gulf Stream shingle. These efforts were organized by MIT/WHOI Joint Program Students under the direction of co-Chief Scientist Glen Gawarkiewicz. A hotwash for this Outreach Student Education and Adaptive Sampling (O-SEAS) component of the cruise is being prepared separately.

Figure 5. Joint Program students and cruise watch leaders, Elena Perez (center right) and Lilli Enders (center left), begin their adaptive sampling through a Gulf Stream shingle by learning from *RV Roger Revelle's* Brent De Vries (left) how an eXpendable BathyThermograph (XBT) can be used to provide a vertical profile of temperature without slowing the ship. Also pictured is Snehal Prabhu (right) of WHOI Operational Scientific Services who processed the shipboard CTD data on RR2407.

In parallel with the NASA/ONR objectives of the MAB-SWOT program described here, we deployed two Popeye Data Shuttle-enabled current and pressure sensor equipped inverted echo sounders (PDS-PIESs, on the continental slope east of the Ocean Observatories Initiative (OOI) Pioneer Array in the southern Mid Atlantic Bight. Data collected during the 4-year deployments will be shared broadly when PDS pods ascend annually to the sea surface and return data batches via a satellite link. Funding for this is provided by the National Science Foundation Division of Ocean Sciences through a RAPID award (NSF-OCE, 2414853). A hotwash of this component of RR2407 is available and is reprinted here: <https://oceanobservatories.org/2024/06/hot-wash-pioneer-adjacent-pies-deployments/>.

Revelle was last at Woods Hole in 2008 and we are happy that the RR2407 Science Party got to help WHOI welcome *Revelle* to the Atlantic as seen on [Instagram](#) and in the [Falmouth Enterprise](#)

RR2407 Chief Sci.: Magdalena Andres | Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI)

¹WHOI subaward from U. North Carolina, Chapel Hill | NASA Ocean Physics Program prime | 1687411

²WHOI subaward from U. of California San Diego | National Ocean Partnership Program (NOPP) Global Internal Wave (NGIW) study | ONR prime | N000142212575

RR2407 Hot Wash: Adaptive Sampling of Gulf Stream Shingle and Shelfbreak Jet

The primary goal of the adaptive sampling plan on the RR2407 cruise was to **generate *in-situ* observations of a Gulf Stream shingle**, a mass of water which separates from a meander crest of the Gulf Stream and is 'left behind' as the jet flows northward. This phenomenon has received little attention since the mid 1980s, but its potential influence on the movements and health of ecologically and commercially important species (ex. squid, scallops) has reinvigorated our interest in the properties of the shingle. In particular, we were interested in collecting data which revealed the vertical extent and structure of the shingle. We first noted the presence of the Gulf Stream shingle in satellite imagery of sea surface temperature (SST) in early June 2024. We monitored the shingle via SST fields as it moved progressively further onshore until we conducted sampling on June 9th and 10th, 2024 as part of cruise RR2407, when the feature was just offshore of the 2000 m isobath. Sampling consisted of CTD profiles (3), XBT deployments (17), surface drifters (2), and underway ADCP measurements (**Figure 1,2**).

Figure 1: Adaptive sampling activities aboard RR2407. Left: Science party prepares to deploy XBT, left to right: Brent De Vries (UCSD), Lilli Enders (MIT-WHOI Joint Program), Elena Perez (MIT-WHOI Joint Program) and Snehal Prabhu (WHOI). Middle: Drifters are deployed as the vessel leaves station. Drifters will return wave and pressure data in real-time, left to right: Nick Carvalho (UMASS Dartmouth), Mason Schettig (USCD), Annette Limoges (UMASS Dartmouth). Right: Nick Carvalho (UMASS Dartmouth, left) and Zach Pereira (UMASS Dartmouth, right) use satellite data to track the Gulf Stream shingle as it migrates further in shore. Photo credits: M. Andres (WHOI, left), L. Enders (MIT-WHOI Joint Program, middle), E. Perez (MIT-WHOI Joint Program, right).

Upon completion of the sampling of the shingle, we identified **underway sampling of the Shelfbreak Jet (SBJ)** as a secondary adaptive sampling goal to be completed up during the remainder of our transit to Woods Hole. To this end, we conducted CTD profiles every 5 nautical miles along the 71 00.00° W longitude line between 39 30.00° N and 40 40.00° N, for a total of nine profiles (**Figure 2**). Underway ADCP measurements were also collected during this period. A drifter was deployed at the second sampling station, with the hopes that it would move southward in the SBJ. The operations completed towards our two science objectives are summarized in Table 1. The data from the adaptive sampling deployments has undergone preliminary processing and is available for further analysis.

Figure 2: Nick Carvalho (UMass Dartmouth). Background contours represent observed Sea Surface Height (SSH).
Courtesy of Elena Perez.

Science Goal	Operation	Date/Time EST (Approx.)	Latitude (Approx.)	Longitude (Approx.)
Shingle Sampling	XBT Deployment	09-June-2024 07:04	37 30.00° N	73 02.52° W
Shingle Sampling	XBT Deployment	09-June-2024 07:59	37 36.00° N	72 57.89° W
Shingle Sampling	XBT Deployment	09-June-2024 09:04	37 42.00° N	72 53.27° W
Shingle Sampling	XBT Deployment	09-June-2024 09:57	37 48.00° N	72 48.64° W
Shingle Sampling	XBT Deployment	09-June-2024 10:51	37 54.00° N	72 44.02° W
Shingle Sampling	CTD Profile	09-June-2024 11:45	38 00.00° N	72 39.39° W
Shingle Sampling	XBT Deployment	09-June-2024 13:23	38 06.00° N	72 34.76° W
Shingle Sampling	XBT Deployment	09-June-2024 14:24	38 12.00° N	72 30.14° W
Shingle Sampling	CTD Profile	09-June-2024 14:54	38 15.00° N	72 27.83° W
Shingle Sampling	XBT Deployment	09-June-2024 16:09	38 18.00° N	72 25.51° W
Shingle Sampling	XBT Deployment	09-June-2024 17:03	38 24.00° N	72 20.89° W
Shingle Sampling	CTD Profile	09-June-2024 17:57	38 30.00° N	72 16.26° W
Shingle Sampling	Drifter Deployment	09-June-2024 18:30	38 30.00° N	72 16.26° W
Shingle Sampling	XBT Deployment	09-June-2024 20:34	38 36.00° N	72 11.63° W
Shingle Sampling	XBT Deployment	09-June-2024 21:28	38 42.00° N	72 07.00° W
Shingle Sampling	XBT Deployment	09-June-2024 22:52	38 48.00° N	72 02.38° W
Shingle Sampling	XBT Deployment	09-June-2024 23:46	38 54.00° N	71 57.76° W
Shingle Sampling	XBT Deployment	10-June-2024 00:40	39 00.00° N	71 53.13° W
SBJ Sampling	CTD Profile	10-June-2024 06:43	39 30.00° N	71 00.00° W
SBJ Sampling	CTD Profile	10-June-2024 09:25	39 40.00° N	71 00.00° W
SBJ Sampling	Drifter Deployment	10-June-2024 10:25	39 40.00° N	71 00.00° W
SBJ Sampling	CTD Profile	10-June-2024 12:05	39 50.00° N	71 00.00° W
SBJ Sampling	CTD Profile	10-June-2024 14:30	40 00.00° N	71 00.00° W
SBJ Sampling	CTD Profile	10-June-2024 15:54	40 05.00° N	71 00.00° W
SBJ Sampling	CTD Profile	10-June-2024 17:06	40 10.00° N	71 00.00° W
SBJ Sampling	CTD Profile	10-June-2024 18:18	39 15.00° N	71 00.00° W
SBJ Sampling	CTD Profile	10-June-2024 19:30	39 20.00° N	71 00.00° W
SBJ Sampling	CTD Profile	10-June-2024 20:42	39 25.00° N	71 00.00° W

Table 01: Summary of all operations conducted for adaptive sampling effort